

ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF BUILDING FLOOR LEVELS ON PASSIVE VENTILATION RATE IN COURTYARD MID-RISE OFFICE BUILDING IN TEMPERATE DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Studies have shown that, people prefer to live in a passive indoor environment than the contrary, and one of the factors affecting that in courtyard buildings is building height. There are limited studies to assess the level of courtyards performance on the building envelope as well as assessing the effects of building height on the ventilation rate. The aim of the study was to evaluate the effects of building heights on ventilation rate in mid-rise office building in temperate dry climate of Nigeria. It was achieved by: determining the level of compliance of courtyard in improving the micro climate of the building in fulfilling the optimum courtyard perimeter and height ratio, optimum courtyard aspect ratio, and minimum openable window to floor area ratio; by also finding the effect of building floor levels on the optimum passive ventilation rate (ach), relative to international standards. Data was collected from simulation of a modelled Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) Senate building as a case study. It was then analysed using an independent-samples t-test with significance threshold of 0.05, bar charts and tables. The study showed that, the courtyard of ABU senate building has no effects on the microclimate of the building, having a courtyard aspect ratio greater than 0.65, and courtyards parameter to height ratio of less than 5. On the effects of building floor levels on ventilation rate, the results showed that, none of the floors have attained optimum ventilation rate except 8th floor. When a series of independent-samples t-test were conducted among the different floor levels, the results showed that, only 8th floor was significantly difference with the others, otherwise all were not significantly different to one another. For example, air changes per hour on the 8th floor was significantly difference with the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th floors with p values of 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000, and 0.0000 respectively. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected and the study concluded that, ventilation rate is only significantly difference at a vertical distance greater than 22m.

Keywords: Air changes per hour, Courtyard aspect ratio, Courtyard parameter to height ratio, Openable window to floor area ratio, OpenStudio.

INTRODUCTION

A number of studies have shown that, people prefer to live within a wider temperature range and other environmental condition than a narrow one (ASRAE standard 55, 2013) and this is only possible within a natural environmental setting. For example, a study by Buys, Summerville, Kennedy, and Bell, (2008) showed that, as many as 83% of people preferred natural ventilation than mechanical means. One of the major challenge in achieving natural ventilation in buildings is the variations of climate with altitude as observed by Sohail, (2017).

Aflaki, Mahyuddin, Mantegi and Bahrum, (2014) have observed that, there were significant differences between mean air temperature and velocity within units in the lower and higher floors of a high-rise building in Malaysia. Zakariaa, Kubotaa, & Toe, (2015) found out that, indoor air temperatures on the ground floor, and the first floor were approximately 0.3 and 1.7°C lower than the corresponding outdoor air temperature during daytime, respectively. Meanwhile, during night-time, the indoor air temperatures in the two floors were merely 0.8 and 1.9°C higher than the outdoors, respectively. Ayode (2004) observed that, temperature decreases with height at an average rate of 6.5°C per kilometer. This is particularly important on a multi-storey courtyard building as observed by Ganem et al. (2014) who noted that, the courtyard in building can improve or worsen microclimatic condition, pending on the kind of attention given to the proportions of courtyard and ventilation strategies. There were few studies of courtyards buildings especially in temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Therefore, the aim of the study was to assess the effects of building height on ventilation rate on mid-rise office building in wet and dry climate of Nigeria. The objectives of the study were: to determine the level of compliance of courtyard design in improving the micro climate of the building in fulfilling the optimum courtyard perimeter and height ratio, optimum courtyard aspect ratio, and minimum openable window to floor area ratio, based on ASHRAE, Meir, Pearlmutter & Etzion, (1995) and Muhaisen & Gadi, (2006b) standards ; to also determine the effect of building floor levels on the optimum passive ventilation rate (ach), relative to international standards. In realizing this goal, the following research questions were raised:

- i. What was the level of compliance for courtyard to improve the microclimatic condition of ABU Senate buildings in fulfilling the openable window to floor area ratio, optimum courtyard perimeter and height ratio, and optimum courtyard aspect ratio?
- ii. To what extent does the different floor levels differ in optimum passive ventilation rate in courtyard mid-rise office building in wet and dry climate of Nigeria?

These brought about the following hypothesis:

- i. The null hypothesis (H_0) states that, the mean effects of passive ventilation rate is significantly the same for all floor levels of courtyard mid-rise office building in wet and dry climate of Nigeria.
- ii. The alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that, the mean effects of passive ventilation rate is

significantly different for at least one of the floors of courtyard mid-rise office building in wet and dry climate of Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1 (2016) defined Ventilation as the practice of providing air to or removing air from a space with the aim of controlling air contaminant levels, humidity, or temperature within the space. The two basic functions of ventilation are: air exchange and air distribution. Air exchange is the frequency of replacement of interior air per hour. It is also known as air changes per hour ACH. ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1 (2004) and 62, (89) recommend that mechanical ventilation should be used when the room ventilation rate is less than 0.35 ach.

Courtyard is a widely used in almost all building typologies and the climatic zones due to its potentials to improve passive indoor comfort. According to historical evidence, the first courtyard houses have originated in India, around 6500-6000 BC (Myneni, 2013). This is partially buttressed by Edwards, Sibley, Hakmi, and, (2006), who observed that,

courtyard buildings had been used since the Neolithic settlements and was extensively used from China to Morocco. Abass, Ismail, & Solla, (2016) defined courtyard as a covered outside space but open to the element at its apex. Mishra & Ramgopal (2013), defined a courtyard as an opened room into the heavens, a square or rectangular in the sketch and bordered by a group of buildings or most important rooms. Koch-Nielsen (2002), defined it as an internal space opened to the sky. Generally, courtyard can be classified into 3 as observed by Berkovic, Yezioro, & Bitan, (2012) and Hyde (2000). These are: fully enclosed courtyard; Semi-enclosed courtyard; and Semi-open courtyard, shown in figure 1. To achieve passive indoor comfort in a courtyard building, the size and design of the courtyard's enclosure have to be carefully considered as observed by Hyde, (2000). For example, Tablada, Blocken, Carmeliet, & De Troyer, (2005) found out that, the courtyard width to height (w/h) ratio would also affect the indoor air flow rate. Muhaisen & Gadi, (2006b) concluded that for a reasonable performance throughout the whole year, courtyards with parameter and height ratio (c/h) equal to or greater than five are recommended.

Fig 1. Courtyard Classification.
Source: Zakaria & Kubota, (2014)

Moreover, Meir, Pearlmutter, & Etzion, (1995) concluded the values of 0.5, 0.65 and above 0.65 ratios as the range for courtyard optimum environmental performance. The study stressed that at an aspect ratio bellow 0.5 the courtyard

is exposed to excessive solar radiation, at about 0.65 the wind velocity and shading are optimum, while greater than 0.65 will lead to a very deep courtyard with little or no ventilation effect at all.

METHODOLOGY

Microclimate data

Most climates classifications that are based on human comfort have their origin from Atkinson (1953)'s climate classification (Koenigsberger, Ingersoll, Mayhew & Szokolay, 2013), who classified climate into: Warm Humid; Hot dry Desert; and Composite Climates. Szokolay, (2008) modified Atkinson's classification to: Cold Climates; Temperate (Moderate) Climates; Hot-Dry Climate; and Warm-Humid Climate. Based on Szokolay's climates classification, Komolafe & Agarwal, (1987) in (Ajibola, 2001), classified Nigerian Climates into: Hot-dry climate; Hot-humid climate; temperate dry climate; and temperate humid climate. The study has adopted Komolafe and Agarwal (1987)'s climate classification based on the fact that, it has been tested and used by a number of researchers, especially those that have worked within Nigerian climates, such as: Nwalusi, Anierobi, Efobi, & Nwokolo, (2015); Ajibola, (2001), etc. Examples of such

areas include towns like Zaria, Kaduna, Plateau, etc.

Research design

A mid-rise office building in this study is any office with 4 to 12 floors, as classified by Alcox (2017) and Freedman (2009). Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) senate building Zaria was selected as a case of fully enclosed courtyard mid-rise office building. It was then modelled using google sketch-up 2017, and open-studio simulation tools. The 6 sets of offices were selected for simulation and analysis, each from first to eighth floors consecutively, making a total of 48 offices. Each set of offices has the same dimensions, orientation, WWR, openable window to floor area ratio and arrangement. Figure 2 shows the East-side of ABU senate building.

An exploratory design approach using quantitative research strategy were employed and a convenience probability sampling technique was used in selecting the building. The criteria used in selection of this building was based on the building type, number of storeys, access to building and HVAC system.

Fig2. Simulated ach in ABU Senate building, Zaria
Source: Field work

The procedure used in conducting the research was based on the following documents:

ASHRAE standards; and Indoor Air Quality Handbook, 2013. Based on those documents the following steps were followed:

- ABU senate building was modelled in google sketch-up (including all properties of materials and ground reflectance) as shown in figure 2.
- In order to simulate ventilation rate (ach), EnergyPlus weather (EPW) was used as the type of weather file.
- Sketch-up plugging called Open-studio was used to set weather files of Zaria from weather Analytic.
- Space types, thermal zones, and construction materials were selected.
- Zone Air change Rate (ach) was selected from output variables.
- Run period from January to December of 2018 was selected from Simulation settings
- Simulation button was pressed for the final analysis

Data generated was then analysed using an independent-samples t-test technique

with significance threshold of 0.05, bar charts, column charts, graphs and tables to find out the effects of building floor levels on ventilation rate in single-banked mid-rise office building in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria.

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

The results of the effects of building floor levels on the passive ventilation rate with respect to openable window to floor area ratio, optimum courtyard perimeter, height ratio, optimum courtyard aspect ratio, and optimum ventilation rate are presented on table 1a, 1b, 1c, 1d, 1e and 1f. The analysis was done based on the benchmarks put forward by professional institutes and other determinants that were discovered in the studies. The minimum passive ventilation rate (ach) as recommended by ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1, (2004) is 0.35 and that of openable area to floor area ratio for natural ventilation in an office space is 4% of the net occupiable floor area (ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1, 2016). The optimum parameter and height ratio is equal to or greater than five Muhaisen & Gadi, (2006b), while 0.65 is the optimum for courtyard aspect ratio (Meir, Pearlmutter, & Etzion, 1995).

Table 1a. Simulation Results for the effects of heights on ventilation of ABU Senate building, Zaria

ABU SENATE BUILDING									
c/h=3.5, w/h=0.73									
Latitude and longitude	11°09'03.11"N / 7°39'20.32"E, 11°09'01.98"N / 7°39'21.21"E, 11°09'02.95"N / 7°39'22.33"E, 11°09'03.96"N / 7°39'21.41"E								
Floor Levels	1 st floor	2 nd floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	7 th floor	8 th floor	
Space Type	110	210	310	410	510	610	710	810	
Orientation	E & N	E & N	E & N	E & N	E & N	E & N	E & N	E & N	E & N

	Dimension	6.6m, 8.4m and 3.048m							
	Window to wall ratio	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%
	Openable Window to floor area ratio	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%
IAQ	Ventilation rate (ach)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.8 in Feb, March, April, May, July, Aug, Oct, Dec

Source: field work, 2018

Where, N, S, E, and W, represent north, south, east and west elevations, while IAQ represents indoor air quality.

Table 1b. Simulation Results for the effects of heights on ventilation of ABU Senate building, Zaria

ABU SENATE BUILDING									
c/h=3.5, w/h=0.73									
Latitude and longitude	11°09'03.11"N / 7°39'20.32"E, 11°09'01.98"N / 7°39'21.21"E, 11°09'02.95"N / 7°39'22.33"E, 11°09'03.96"N / 7°39'21.41'								
Floor Levels		1 st floor	2 nd floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	7 th floor	8 th floor
-	Space Type	107	207	307	407	507	607	707	807
	Orientation	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E
	Dimensions	6.5m, 6.6m and 3.048m							
	Window to wall ratio	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%
	Openable Window to floor area ratio	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%
IAQ	Ventilation rate (ach)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.93 ach in Jan, Feb, March, April, May, July, Aug, Sept, Oct, Dec

Source: field work, 2018

Table 1c. Simulation Results for the effects of heights on ventilation of ABU Senate building, Zaria

ABU SENATE BUILDING									
c/h=3.5, w/h=0.73									
Latitude and longitude	11°09'03.11"N / 7°39'20.32"E, 11°09'01.98"N / 7°39'21.21"E, 11°09'02.95"N / 7°39'22.33"E, 11°09'03.96"N / 7°39'21.41"E								
Floor Levels		1 st floor	2 nd floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	7 th floor	8 th floor
Space Type		106	206	306	406	506	606	706	806
Orientation		W	W	W	W	W	W	W	W
Dimensions		6.6m, 4.5m, and 3.048 m	6.6m, 4.5m, and 3.048m						
Window to wall ratio		5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%
Openable Window to floor area ratio		6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%
IAQ	Ventilation rate (ach)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.7 ach in Feb, March, April, July, Aug, Sept Oct, Dec

Source: field work, 2018

Table 1d. Simulation Results for the effects of heights on ventilation of ABU Senate building, Zaria

ABU SENATE BUILDING									
c/h=3.5, w/h=0.73									
Latitude and longitude	11°09'03.11"N / 7°39'20.32"E, 11°09'01.98"N / 7°39'21.21"E, 11°09'02.95"N / 7°39'22.33"E, 11°09'03.96"N / 7°39'21.41"E								
Floor Levels		1 st floor	2 nd floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	7 th floor	8 th floor
Space Type		110	210	310	410	510	610	710	810
Dimensions		6.6m, 8.4m and 3.048 m	6.6m, 8.4m and 3.048m	6.6m, 8.4m and 3.048 m	6.6m, 8.4m and 3.048m				
Orientation		E & S	E & S	E & S	E & S	E & S	E & S	E & S	E &
Openable Window to		7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%	7.4%

	floor area ratio								
	Window to wall ratio	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%	12.1%
IAQ	Ventilation rate (ach)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
									in Feb, March, April, Aug, Sept, Oct,

Source: field work, 2018

Table 1e. Simulation Results for the effects of heights on ventilation of ABU Senate building, Zaria

ABU SENATE BUILDING									
c/h=3.5, w/h=0.73									
Latitude and longitude	11°09'103.11"N / 7°39'120.32"E, 11°09'01.98"N / 7°39'21.21"E, 11°09'02.95"N / 7°39'22.33"E, 11°09'03.96"N / 7°39'21.41"E								
Floor Levels		1st floor	2nd floor	3rd floor	4th floor	5th floor	6th floor	7th floor	8th floor
Space Type		107	207	307	407	507	607	707	807
Orientation		S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Dimension		6.5m, 6.6m and 3.048 m	6.5m, 6.6m and 3.048m						
Openable Window to floor area ratio		7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%	7.1%
Window to wall ratio		6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%	6.8%
IAQ	Ventilation rate (ach)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.9 ac in Jan, Feb, March, April, May, July, Aug, Sept, Oct, Dec

Source: field work, 2018

Table 1e. Simulation Results for the effects of heights on ventilation of ABU Senate building, Zaria

ABU SENATE BUILDING									
c/h=3.5, w/h=0.73									
Latitude and longitude	11°09'03.11"N / 7°39'20.32"E, 11°09'01.98"N / 7°39'21.21"E, 11°09'02.95"N / 7°39'22.33"E, 11°09'03.96"N / 7°39'21.41"								
Floor Levels		1 st floor	2 nd floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	7 th floor	8 th floor
Space Type		106	206	306	406	506	606	706	806
Dimensions		6.6m, 4.5m, and 3.048 m	6.6m, 4.5m, and 3.048m						
Orientation		N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Openable Window to floor area ratio		6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%	6.5%
Window to wall ratio		5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%	5.7%
IAQ	Ventilation rate (ach)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	Feb, march, April, Aug, Sept, Oct,

Source: field work, 2018

For the purpose of Hypothesis testing a Microsoft Excel Data Analysis Pack was used to analyse data from the open-studio simulation tool to find out the value of statistical significance of the effects of floor levels on ventilation rate of the mid-rise office building in wet and dry climate of Nigeria. The research was analysed and discussed based on the Hypothesis testing and research questions earlier raised in this paper as follows.

The first question was that:

What is the level of compliance for courtyard to improve the microclimatic condition of ABU Senate buildings in fulfilling the openable window to floor area ratio, optimum courtyard perimeter and height ratio, and optimum courtyard aspect ratio?

From table 1a to 1f, it could be observed that, all the offices have complied with the ASHRAE Standard 62.1 (2016) of

having 4% openable window to floor area ratio. It can also be noted that,

Fig 3. Comparison of courtyard perimeter to height ratio of the ABU senate building and the optimum Standard in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria.
Source: Field work, 2018

Courtyard of ABU Senate building is below the standard threshold of courtyard perimeter to height ratio as shown on figure 3 and also above the optimum value of courtyard aspect ratio as indicated in figure 4

Fig 4. Comparison of courtyard aspect ratio of the ABU senate building and the optimum Standard in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria.
Source: Field work, 2018

This shows that, the courtyard is not in any way facilitating the passive ventilation neither improving the sun shading of the building. This is because of the courtyard aspect ratio greater than 0.65, which according to Meir, Pearlmuter, & Etzion, (1995), will have no ventilation effect at all. Moreover, Muhaisen, & Gadi, (2006b), has opined that, for a reasonable environmental performance throughout the whole year, courtyards with parameter and height

ratio equal to or greater than five are recommended. The next research question is that:

To what extent does the different floor levels differ in optimum passive ventilation rate in courtyard mid-rise office building in wet and dry climate of Nigeria?

The descriptive results showed that, none of the floors have attained optimum ventilation rate except on the last floor (8th floor) as shown in figure 6. This can

be justified due to significant difference of indoor air velocity in the lower and upper levels as observed by Aflaki,

Mahyuddin, Mantegi and Bahrum, (2014).

Fig 5. Comparison of optimum air changes per hour among the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th floors in 48 offices of courtyard mid-rise office building in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria. Source: Field work, 2018

Fig 6. Comparison of air changes per hour among the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th floors in 48 offices of courtyard mid-rise office building in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria. Source: Field work, 2018

A further analysis indicated that, the building floor levels affect ventilation rate at a vertical distance greater than 22m as shown in figure 6. This explains why none of the floor is significantly different with one another except with the 8th floor.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀ Null Hypothesis: the mean effects of passive ventilation rate are significantly the same for all floor levels of courtyard

mid-rise office building in wet and dry climate of Nigeria.

For the relationship between 8th and other floors (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th)

The independent-samples t-test were conducted to compare the effects of ach, in 48 offices between 8 consecutives floors of single-banked mid-rise office building.

The results showed that there was significant difference in the ach between offices on the 8th floor (M=8.2, SD=1.84) and the offices on 1st floor of the mid-rise office building (M=0, SD=0) conditions; $t(5)= 10.90, p=0.0000$; that there was significant difference in the ach-value, between offices on the 8th floor (M=8.2, SD=1.84) and the offices on 2nd floor of the mid-rise office building (M=0, SD=0) conditions; $t(5)= 10.90, p=0.0000$; that there was significant difference in the ach-value, between offices on the 8th floor (M=8.2, SD=1.84) and the offices on 3rd floor of the mid-rise office building (M=0, SD=0) conditions; $t(5)= 10.90, p=0.0000$; that there was significant difference in the ach-value between offices on the 8th floor (M=8.2, SD=1.84) and the offices on 4th floor of the mid-rise office building (M=0, SD=0) conditions; $t(5)= 10.90, p=0.0000$; that there was significant difference in the ach-value between offices on the 8th floor (M=8.2, SD=1.84) and the offices on 5th floor of the mid-rise office building (M=0, SD=0) conditions; $t(5)= 10.90, p=0.0000$; that there was significant difference in the ach, between offices on the 8th floor (M=8.2, SD=1.84) and the offices on 6th floor of the mid-rise office building (M=0, SD=0) conditions; $t(5)= 10.90, p=0.0000$; that there was significant difference in the ach between offices on the 8th floor (M=8.2, SD=1.84) and the offices on 7th floor of the mid-rise office building (M=0, SD=0) conditions; $t(5)= 10.90, p=0.0000$.

From the above results, the null hypothesis was therefore rejected, and the results showed that, 8th and above floors should be given special considerations in terms of WWR, openable window to floor area ratio and window positioning.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This reserch have shown that, the courtyard of ABU Senate building has no effect in facilitating the passive ventilation of the building, with the courtyard aspect ratio greater than 0.65, and courtyards parameter to height ratio less than 5. These have not complied with the recommendations of Meir, Pearlmutter, & Etzion, (1995) and Muhaisen, & Gadi, (2006b) respectively.

On the effects of building heights on ventilation rate, the results showed that, none of the floors have attained optimum ventilation rate except the 8th. When a series of independent-samples t-test were conducted among the different floor levels, the results showed that, only 8th floor was significantly difference with the others, otherwise all were not significantly different to one another. For example, air changes per hour on the 8th floor was significantly difference with the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th floors with p values of 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000, and 0.0000 respectively. This shows that, ventilation rate is only significantly different at a vertical distance greater than 22m.

The study rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that, ventilation rate is only significantly difference at a vertical distance greater than 22m of Courtyard mid-rise office buildings in temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

The study recommends that:

- i. The openable area to floor area ratio must be designed based on floor levels.
- ii. For offices located greater than 22m high, wider inlet opening should be used due to the strong

wind condition, as this helps to decrease the wind velocity at the inlet opening (Rizk, El-Morsi & Elwan, 2018).

- iii. For offices located at less than 22m high, corner locations of the inlet and outlet openings are recommended due to the lower wind velocity at the corner locations. Alternatively, larger width of the outlet opening than the inlet is recommended, this is due to their weak wind conditions and therefore helps to increase the wind velocity at the inlet opening.

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